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A STUDY ABOUT WORKING CAPITAL MANAGEMENT

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Abstract:

The term working capital management is a business tool that helps the company effectively make use of current asset and maintain sufficient cash flow to meet short-term goals and obligations. By effectively maintain cash flow they may able to reduce the need of external borrowing, expand their businesses, fund managers and acquisitions or invest in research and development. Company needs to have enough cash balance to cover both planned costs and unexpected cost, while making best use of available funds. This achieved by the effective management of account payable, account receivable, inventory, and cash. Equally, shortening the cash conversion cycle also improves the firm's profitability.

Keywords:

working capital management, account receivable, account payable, cash conversion cycle.

Introduction:

Working capital management is designed by strategy is to ensure that a company operates efficiently by monitoring and using current assets and liabilities in the best effect. The primary source of working capital management is to enable the company to maintain sufficient cash flow to meet its short-term operating costs and short-term obligations. A company's working capital made up of its current asset minus current liabilities. Current asset includes of any asset which easily convertible into cash in 12 months. These are the company's highly liquid assets. Some current assets include cash, accounts receivable, inventory, and short-term investments. Current liabilities are any obligations due within the following 12 months. These include accruals for operating expenses and current portions of long-term debt payments. Working capital management commonly involves monitoring cash flow, current assets, and current liabilities through ratio analysis of the key elements of working capital, including the working capital ratio, collection ratio, and inventory turnover ratio. It helps maintain the smooth operation of the net operating cycle, also known as the cash conversion cycle (CCC)- the minimum amount of time required to convert net current assets and liabilities into cash. Working capital management can improve a company's cash flow management and earnings quality through efficient use of its resources. Management of working capital includes inventory management as well as management of accounts receivables and accounts payables. Working capital management also involves the timing of payables. A company can conserve cash by choosing to stretch the payment of suppliers and to make the most of available credit or may spend cash by purchasing using cash - these choices also affect working capital management.

Working Capital Ratio:**Current Ratio:**

The current ratio (working capital ratio) is a company's current assets divided by current liabilities. It is a key indicator of a company's financial health as it demonstrates its ability to meet its short-term financial obligations. Current ratios of 1.2 to 2.0 are considered desirable, but a ratio higher than 2.0 may suggest that the company is not managing its working capital efficiently. Conversely, a current ratio below 1.0 generally indicates that a company's debts due in the upcoming year would not be covered by its liquid assets.

Current Ratio= Current Asset/Current Liabilities.

Collection Ratio:

The collection ratio, or days sales outstanding (DSO), is a measure of how efficiently a company manages its accounts receivables. It is calculated as the product of the number of days in an accounting period multiplied by the average amount of outstanding accounts receivables divided by the total amount of net credit sales during the accounting period. Essentially, this ratio shows how effective a company is at collecting payment after a sales transaction on credit. The lower a company's collection ratio, the more efficient its cash flow.

Day Sales Outstanding (DSO) - the average number of days taken for the company's customers to pay their invoices.

Inventory Ratio:

Companies typically measure how efficiently that balance is maintained by monitoring the inventory turnover ratio. The inventory turnover ratio, calculated as cost of goods sold divided by average balance sheet inventory, reveals how rapidly a company's inventory is being used in sales and replaced. A relatively low ratio compared to industry peers indicates a risk that inventory levels are excessively high, while a relatively high ratio may indicate inadequate inventory levels.

Days Inventory Outstanding (DIO) - the average number of days that the company takes to sell its inventory.

Payable Ratio:

Days payable outstanding (DPO) is a useful working capital ratio used in finance departments that measures how many days, on average, it takes a company to pay its suppliers. As such, DPO is an important consideration when it comes to managing a company's account payable – in other words, the amount owed to creditors and suppliers. The higher a company's DPO, the longer it takes to pay its bills.

Days Payable Outstanding (DPO) - the average number of days that the company takes to pay its suppliers.

Cash Conversion Cycle:

The cash conversion cycle (CCC) – also known as the cash cycle – is a working capital metric which expresses how many days it takes a company to convert cash into inventory, and then back into cash via the sales process. The shorter a company's CCC, the less time a company has cash tied up in its accounts receivable and inventory. The CCC is an important metric for companies that buy and manage inventory as it is an indication of operational efficiency as well as financial health. That said, it should not be looked at in isolation, but in conjunction with other financial metrics such as return on equity. It is also important to note that CCC is not a significant consideration for all companies, as not every organization will hold physical inventory.

Cash Conversion Cycle (CCC) - the average time taken for the company to convert its investment in inventory into cash.

$$CCC = DIO + DSO - DPO$$

Objectives of Working Capital Management:

- **Meeting obligations.** Working capital management should always ensure that the business has enough liquidity to meet its short-term obligations, often by collecting payment from customers sooner or by extending supplier payment terms. Unexpected costs can also be considered obligations, so these need to be factored into the approach to working capital management, too.
- **Growing the business.** With that said, it's also important to use your short-term assets effectively, whether that means supporting global expansion or investing in R&D. If your company's assets are tied up in inventory or accounts payable, the business may not be as profitable as it could be. In other words, too cautious an approach to working capital management is suboptimal.
- **Optimizing capital performance.** Another working capital management objective is to optimize the efficiency of capital usage – whether by minimizing capital costs or maximizing capital returns. The former can be achieved by reclaiming capital that is currently tied up to reduce the need for borrowing, while the latter involves ensuring the ROI of spare capital outweighs the average cost of financing it.

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Improve Working Capital Management:

Companies can have wide range of solutions for effective working capital management, both for themselves and suppliers.

Cash Flow Forecasting:

By forecasting future cash flows – such as payables and receivables. Companies can plan for any upcoming cash gaps and make better use of any surpluses. The more accurately you can predict your future cash flows, the better-informed your working capital management decisions will be effective for business.

Supply Chain Finance:

For buyers, supply chain finance – also known as reverse factoring it is a way of offering suppliers early payment via one or more third-party funders. Suppliers can improve their DSO by getting paid sooner at a low cost of funding – while buyers can preserve their own working capital by paying in line with agreed payment terms.

Reduce inventory and increase inventory turnover

For middle-market firms that carry inventory, well-managed inventory management may be the most powerful leverage to working capital improvements. Achieving a higher net working capital calculation can be achieved by reducing slow-moving inventory, increasing the inventory turnover cycles, and avoiding stockpiling. Although inventory is considered an asset in the working capital formula, less inventory on the shelves equates to more freed up cash flow. Optimizing inventory through the lens of working capital includes inventory management processes and analysing inventory performance metrics. Utilizing the inventory turnover ratio or days inventory outstanding (DIO) metrics that reveal the average number of days a company holds its inventory before selling it will allow a company to better understand its inventory turnover. An analytical working capital management team will periodically measure turnover rates, compare it to industry competitors, and uncover opportunities to reduce their DIO that result in increased savings and working capital. Efficient inventory management can have a significant impact on accounts receivables, accounts payables, operations, and overall profitability and growth.

Dynamic Discounting:

Dynamic discounting is another solution that buyers can use to provide early payment to suppliers – but this time there's no external funder, as the program is funded by the buyer via early payment discounts. Like supply chain finance, this enables suppliers to reduce their DSO. What's more, it allows buyers to achieve an attractive risk-free return on their excess cash.

Flexible Funding:

Last but not least, working capital providers that offer flexible funding may allow buyers to move seamlessly between supply chain finance and dynamic discounting models, meaning companies can adapt to their varying working capital needs while continuing to support their suppliers.

Conclusion:

Good management of working capital shall ensure that a business has the cash and resources available to have successful and healthy business operations and meet its current liabilities, without which a company shall always be under the risk of having a working capital deficit thereby hampering its business operations. In the short term this can damage the profitability of the business, and affect its operations. In the long term, poor working capital management can compromise a company's eligibility for business loans and damage its ability to attract potential investors. In recent times, there have been greater bankruptcies on account of working capital deficits and unmanaged cash flows such that companies have not been able to repay their debt obligations. The right systems and policies in place to manage business operations as well as the right mix of financial products and facilities from banks and financial institutions to ensure cost effective liquidity shall enable companies to manage such risks of working capital deficits and maintain a healthy business cycle.

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